

THE UTILIZATION OF MONTESSORI – PEDAGOGY AND ITS METHODS FOR PRESCHOOLERS AND SCHOOLERS IN RUSSIA

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the emergence of Montessori pedagogy, its study, implementation in the educational system, methods of use and observation, results and research, main problems during the period of the article for preschool and school educational in Russia. Moreover this article is devoted to the parents who concluded that their uncommon youngster should have been given an exceptional instruction that would transform him into a free, capable individual. The article presents a model of pedagogical support for the social adaptation of children with disabilities. It involves taking into account the important psycho-pedagogical positions: the formation of a child-centered interaction of instructor with children, diagnosis and development of individual characteristics of children, taking into account the characteristics of sensitive periods of the child's psyche. Additionally, the methodological part puts stress on didactic aids and materials, where the dominant things are children's fingers. Montessori's experience has shown that kids' formative climate ought to imitate the grown-up one, and that implies the first toys ought to be things that we grown-ups typically use in regular day to day existence. In such a climate, the child rapidly learns also, recollects the essential laws of the world. Among the determined illuminating the Montessori – pedagogy presences and proceeds with its excursion, including an ever increasing number of nations, instructors and kids.

Introduction. Parents who decided that their extraordinary child needed to be given an extraordinary education that would turn him into a free, responsible person. They wanted their child to develop hormonally, without pressure from adults, without cramming,

exhausting exams and grades, through his own discoveries, through freedom of choice and movement, so that he could grow up to be who he really is. They found all this in the kindergartens and schools of Maria Montessori.

Learning from the first days of life has long been part of our lives, because modern scientists and teachers believe that children begin to learn too late at 6-7 years old, when the main neural connections in the brain have already been formed. Even before birth, the child's body begins a vibrant life: vision, hearing, smell, taste and touch develop. A child needs to adapt to new conditions; information is a vital necessity for him. His brain works all the time, learning to compare and draw conclusions. "I left Italy in 1934, when all my schools were closed" is a unique chronicle, an interview with a teacher who, according to UNESCO recognition, defined the way of pedagogical thinking of the twentieth century. A crater on Venus is named after her, her image is on postage stamps of dozens of countries around the world, and in her homeland in Italy she is revered as the greatest person. Montessori became the creator of a new pedagogical system, which changed all ideas about this science.

Method

"She approached the creation of a pedagogical system like a real scientist, and her book is called that - <<Scientific Pedagogy>> (1909, Italy). The methods that she used to create this new system were truly truly scientific" - cited Irina Fedosova, director of the National Institute for Quality Education, Moscow. [2] After receiving degrees in psychiatry and pediatrics, Montessori visited orphanages for orphans with various disorders, and soon noticed that children learned about the world around them in the most accessible way - through sensory experiences. And the more agile the children's fingers became, and the more varied the materials for children's research, the faster the children began to speak, understood better and pronounced words faster, and developed better. Then Maria came up with her unusual aids and materials, which went down in history as the "golden material of Montessori." For instance, a five-year-old girl cooks scrambled eggs on a real stove, another one nearby twists a water tap, a third child draws, a fourth builds a huge tower of geometric shapes or solves mathematical problems. The Montessori method is based on observing the child and accepting him as he is and what he may become in the future, but respect for the individual child and benevolent patience.

The main principle is to create conditions for self-education, self-training and self-development. The teacher follows the child as he reveals his inner capabilities. Montessori's motto: "Help me do it myself!" Observing children of different ages, Montessori created a special developmental environment for them, where there are activities for the development of different children's needs and interests.

Didactic aids and materials were designed so that the child could independently detect and correct his mistakes, develop will, patience, observation, learn self-discipline, and most importantly, show his own activity. Carefully thought out to the smallest detail and beautifully designed didactic material stimulates the natural development of the child, offering him a holistic picture of the world.

"Motility is the development of the fine muscles of the hand and our hand is a very developed instrument of ours. If we build a map of the brain, then in the brain our hand makes up the largest part relative to other parts of our body, so when a child up to three years old

begins to pour cereals, shift small objects, insert something somewhere, he trains the small muscles of his hand. When his hand becomes dexterous, he is able to make precise and subtle movements, he is able to take a pencil with a pen, write letters, assemble small parts of a construction set" claimed Anna Boyarintsova, leading researcher Institute for the Study of Childhood, Family and Education RAE (Russian Academy of Education), Moscow. [1] When a child assembles cylinders, arranges sticks and builds a pyramid, he develops color perception. He learns to coordinate movements, concentrate, and at the same time prepares to study mathematics.

Results and Discussion

"It seems that everything is quite simple. The child assembles a pink tower, from large to small, the cubes stack on top of each other, but at this moment the main thing happens, the child penetrates into the very essence of the classification. And we already see how at first he simply plays with the cubes, and then he easily assembles this tower, and then goes on to experiment with the following materials," quoted Irina Fedosova. [2] Montessori's experience has shown that children's developmental environment should replicate the adult one, which means the first toys should be things that we adults usually use in everyday life. In such an environment, the baby quickly learns and remembers the basic laws of the world. For example, water is flowing, wet, spills, glass breaks, sand spills, objects are wide and narrow, large and small.

"The Montessori didactic kit itself prompted teachers around the world to search for more and more new didactic materials that really give the child the opportunity to self-learn," mentioned Irina Fedosova. [2]

What happens in Montessori kindergartens initially surprises a person with a classical idea of a kindergarten. Children in groups of different ages. In the first group there are from 1 to 3 years-old, in the second from 3 to 6. As a rule, this raises a lot of questions for parents. "What is the Montessori method? This is socialization. These are large groups of children, and in these large groups, nevertheless, the process is organized in such a way that each child is not only comfortable, but also successfully educated. Since his unique characteristics are taken into account," reported Nadezhda Smirnova, Director of the International Institute of Montessori Pedagogy, Moscow. [11]

In Russia there is now a lot of talk about inclusive education, when children with special needs study in kindergarten or school together with healthy children. This practice existed initially in the Montessori system. This means that there are always several children with special needs in the class. This actually allows not only a child with special needs to be part of a children's team, but it greatly helps other children.

In order to teach and educate himself, he does not need to be punished or encouraged. It is necessary to create the necessary conditions, "throwing a coal into the furnace of his mind." Adults establish order, and the child develops within this order, but at his own rhythm and pace, according to his individual needs.

In a regular kindergarten, as a rule, the teacher chooses what the child will do. Why torment him with the problem of choice? A Montessori teacher acts differently. He observes the child's choice and is ready to help him master the chosen subject. If the child does not

know how to use the manual, he will show what can be done with this or that object by showing an individual lesson presentation.

The Montessori classroom space is a space of choice, divided into several centers of activity, into several zones. Here the child learns to peel and cut vegetables, set the table, fasten buttons, hooks and buttons, tie shoelaces and many other things. Most ordinary household items are freely available, and a little person, under the guidance of a teacher, masters skills important for future life.

From birth until about 5 and a half years of age, the child's need for sensory sensations is especially great. He receives any new information for himself through his senses. All touch zone materials are carefully thought out and developed. Working with them, the child not only develops fine and gross motor skills, masters the algorithm of actions, develops thinking, but also refines perception. The child learns to distinguish temperature by touching ice, metal objects heated in the sun, pebbles, or immersing his hands in warm water.

The math zone contains materials that allow you to teach your child the basics of mathematics. He simply lives in an environment saturated with mathematics. Counting material differs in color, shape, and surface texture. Children master counting skills, basic mathematical symbols, and writing numbers into simple operations.

In the natural-science zone, the child gains knowledge about the world around him, about the relationships and interactions of phenomena, about the history and culture of peoples. Here he realizes himself as a particle of the universe and learns to accept responsibility for it. Maria Montessori called this cosmic education.

"It can't be! Children at 4 years old can't write!" everyone said. But they want to, said Montessori," cited Irina Fedosova. [2] Soon in Russia, in addition to kindergartens, the first schools based on the Maria Montessori education system appeared. Most of us are familiar with classic classroom teaching where the teacher is in complete control. In a Montessori school, on the contrary, the main thing is the student. He himself chooses what is more interesting and important for him to do now, in which direction to develop his abilities.

The Montessori school method has again made an offer that gives children the opportunity to continue to explore themselves, but at a more complex stage. "In the classroom, all conditions have been created for the child to understand: What am I? What do I like? Where does my interest lie? What am I good at? And what am I not good at? And this provides an opportunity in the future. Already by the ninth grade, there is an exact understanding of why a child wants to connect his life", mentioned Yulia Nikishina, co-founder of the Montessori school <<Земляне>>, Moscow. [10]

All this does not mean at all that traditional school subjects are not studied in a Montessori school. There is arithmetic, geometry, and languages, but they are taught on a different principle. Not boring science, but in the form of independent research, all with the same golden Montessori materials that give the classes a practical quality. Learning comes through discovery and this is one of the fundamental principles of the system. "If in kindergarten the materials are objects, then in school these are tests, worksheets, cards of different timelines that will allow the child to study science," claimed Valentina Mikhailova, director of the Montessori Mikhailova School, St. Petersburg.[4] The Montessori education system gives the child not some fragmentary knowledge that children receive in a modern

secondary school, but a holistic picture of the world. After all, botany is inseparable from zoology, and literature from history. There are no grades given at a Montessori school; the students themselves keep track of the work they have done. This could be a journal or a diagram. There is no need to yell at the child, force, coerce, no one compares C students with excellent students. Children learn freely without coercion, external interference or criticism.

In a Montessori school, as in a kindergarten, there are classes of different ages from 6 to 9 years old, and from 9 to 12. The principle, as in kindergarten, is that the older ones help the younger ones. No mandatory sitting at desks. The student lives in a developing environment, only much richer than in the kindergarten. Zones of the prepared environment are transformed. They become more rich, scientific and educational materials according to age.

Models and maps, simulators and cards, textbooks and encyclopedias, microscopes and computers appear at school, but the principle of a clear division of the educational space into thematic zones remains unchanged. Despite the differences in ages from 6 to 12 years old, the materials in the classroom are almost the same. This gives schoolchildren the opportunity to return again and again to the presentations that they mastered at the very beginning throughout their years of study.

Maria Montessori described the age from 6 to 12 years as a transition to a new level of development. At 4 years old, the child was interested in objects, working with his hands, and remembering names. Now he wants to understand how and why. That is, to understand cause and effect relationships.

The task of a Montessori school teacher is to give him the information and material necessary to comprehend the interconnectedness and integrity of the world. However, in some Russian Montessori schools there are already classes where children study right up to graduation, and there are groups for the youngest, from 0 to 3 years old, in which parents learn to understand him from the first days of their child's life.

Conclusion. Charming as childhood, Montessori pedagogy burst into the 20th century like a meteorite. Among the calculated luminaries and continues its journey, involving more and more countries, teachers and children. Such an organic fusion of various knowledge about man, which is provided by science and philosophy, religion and art, collected into a holistic anthropology, moreover, equipped with subtle didactic and methodological tools, has never been seen in world experience.

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